

Architecture Design and Specification Report V1

Deliverable 2.2

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This deliverable was developed based on collective efforts from all partners of the consortium.

Glossary and Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
DT	Digital Twin
EDI	Electronic Data Interchange
GDS	Geographically Distributed Co-Simulation
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HIL	Hardware-in-the-Loop
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
ONS	Operador Nacional do Sistema (Brasil) Brazil's electricity system operator
PV	Photovoltaic
RBAC	Role-Based Access Control
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
WEC	Wave Energy Converters

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Executive Summary

The ORION architecture is designed as a modular and flexible system, enabling the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI), Digital Twins (DTs), data analytics, and simulation tools. Its layered structure supports data collection, ingestion, processing, storage, and visualization, ensuring efficient management and optimization of renewable energy assets. The toolbox is structured to accommodate five distinct use cases, each with specific requirements, while maintaining a common core architecture that ensures data governance, standardization, and compliance with international regulations.

A key aspect of this architecture is its ability to facilitate internal and external communications via APIs (Application Programming Interfaces). These APIs enable efficient data exchange between toolbox components, external energy platforms, and research institutions. Internal APIs manage structured data flow within ORION, supporting data monitoring, AI-driven analytics, and predictive maintenance models. External APIs establish connectivity with third-party services, including SCADA systems, cloud computing platforms, and European digital infrastructures.

The Processing & Analytics layer of the ORION platform integrates AI models, simulation tools, and optimization algorithms to enhance fault detection, predictive maintenance, and decision-making. It ensures that data can be analysed efficiently, supporting both on-platform execution and externally processed computations, as planned for the Canadian and Brazilian use cases, where advanced simulations and AI processing occur externally.

The Data Storage and Management layer provides secure, structured, and standardized storage, ensuring compliance with GDPR and international data governance policies. It supports structured, semi-structured, and unstructured data, making it adaptable to diverse energy scenarios.

The Interface & Visualization layer incorporates interactive dashboards, graphical Digital Twins, heatmaps, and augmented reality tools, enabling stakeholders to monitor operations, simulate scenarios, and optimize performance. Integration with Electronic Document Interchange (EDI) ensures secure data exchange with external stakeholders.

Finally, the ORION Modular Toolbox supports long-term evolution, allowing new tools, methodologies, and emerging technologies to be incorporated seamlessly. The system's modular and standards-compliant approach ensures that ORION remains a scalable and replicable solution that supports the digital transformation of renewable energy infrastructures.

1. Introduction

1.1. About the project

The ORION project aims to advance European leadership in science and technology by developing a modular and scalable digital architecture to support the energy transition. The project focuses on creating a Digital Twin framework that integrates AI-driven analytics, data interoperability, and advanced sensor networks to optimize the operation of renewable energy assets, including hydro, solar, wind, and wave energy systems.

1.2. Objectives of D2.2

This document aims to provide global functional specifications and a high-level technical design for the general architecture of the ORION modular toolbox. It is the foundation for the information exchange interface between different modules, external systems, and stakeholders. The architecture encompasses all components supporting its functionalities, including internal and external communication interfaces (APIs) that enable seamless interaction between the toolbox tools and services.

The modules within this architecture are structured to perform specific functions, including data gathering, transfer, and storage; signal-based AI data analytics; modelling and simulation tools for Digital Twins (DTs); and asynchronous or synchronous access to both real and simulated data. These specifications align with existing standards, such as IEC 61724, and best practice guidelines at both European and international levels.

A key aspect of this architecture is the API communication framework, which includes functional blocks, data flows, and connectors. This framework is essential to ensure efficient data exchange between components and stakeholders while guaranteeing the replicability and scalability of the modules and tools beyond the project's scope.

This deliverable was developed in the context of WP2, which had the following objectives:

- ✓ Conduct a comprehensive mapping of ORION technologies' state-of-the-art as a foundation for the project's developments.
- ✓ Define ORION's overall architecture design, identifying the needs and requirements for interaction between different layers and technologies while ensuring interoperability and alignment with the five use cases.
- ✓ Ensure proper data governance, compliance with GDPR, and alignment with relevant international regulations applicable to Cape Verde, Brazil, and Canada.

By establishing a structured framework for developing and integrating digital solutions, this deliverable plays a key role in ensuring that the digital transformation of the energy value chain is carried out efficiently, securely, and sustainably.

1.3. Targets of D2.2

This deliverable is primarily addressed to ORION consortium members, particularly those responsible for designing, developing, and integrating the modular toolbox components. It provides a structured framework and guidelines to ensure interoperability, scalability, and compliance with international standards throughout the project lifecycle.

Additionally, this document serves as a reference for:

- Technical teams developing and implementing the Digital Twin architecture, AI-driven analytics, and data management solutions.
- Work Package (WP) leaders oversee the alignment between different project activities and ensure seamless interaction between modules.
- Regulatory and compliance experts, ensuring that data governance, GDPR compliance, and international regulations (applicable to Cape Verde, Brazil, and Canada) are properly integrated into the system architecture.
- External stakeholders, including research institutions, energy industry partners, and policymakers, who may leverage ORION's technological framework for future applications beyond the project's scope.

By defining the high-level architecture and functional specifications, this deliverable ensures that all stakeholders involved in ORION's digital ecosystem can collaborate effectively, fostering a secure, interoperable, and scalable framework.

1.4. Methodology

The methodology adopted for developing this deliverable follows a structured approach to ensure that the proposed architecture aligns with the project objectives and the specific needs of the involved partners.

Initially, a thorough review of the Grant Agreement was conducted to extract the key requirements and definitions for the high-level architecture. This step provided a foundation for understanding the scope and fundamental components of the architecture. Subsequently, an analysis was carried out to determine the role and interactions of each partner within the architecture, classifying them according to their function as end users, data providers/owners, or technology developers. The latter category includes those responsible for information processing technologies, developing models and algorithms, and co-simulation tools.

Beyond defining the general structure of the high-level architecture, a series of meetings are held with partners to gather additional insights. These discussions aim to clarify the specificities of each use case, determine which modules are applied in different scenarios, and map the information flow within the architecture. This collaborative approach ensures the architecture design is technically robust and aligned with the project's real-world applications.

Additionally, an essential step in developing this document is its validation phase, during which partners review the content, provide feedback, and contribute to further refinements before the final submission. This iterative process guarantees that the document accurately reflects the requirements and expectations of all stakeholders.

Version 1 of this deliverable focuses on defining the high-level structure of the architecture, establishing its core components, and detailing the interactions between partners. This initial version provides a foundational framework that will be further refined through partner contributions and iterative validation.

1.5. Document Structure

This report is structured to provide an overview of the ORION Modular Toolbox architecture, detailing its components, functionalities, and communication mechanisms. The sections of the document are as follows:

The **Introduction** outlines the objectives, scope, and methodology of the ORION project, explaining the purpose of this deliverable within the broader project context.

A **General System Description** introduces the ORION Modular Toolbox, describing its core features, main functionalities, and the key stakeholders involved in its development and implementation.

The **General Architecture** section defines the high-level system requirements and design, detailing the layered structure and how different components interact.

The **Internal and External Communications** section describes the APIs framework, focusing on structured data integration and interoperability between ORION tools and external platforms.

The **Technical Specifications of Components** provides a detailed breakdown of the main modules, including their configuration, dependencies, and integration within the ORION platform.

Security and regulatory compliance are addressed in the Security and Compliance section, which outlines the policies governing data protection, access control, and adherence to standards such as GDPR.

The **Evolution Plan** identifies potential improvements and outlines the next steps for refining and expanding the ORION architecture in future iterations.

In conclusion, the key contributions of the deliverable are summarized, emphasizing its role in supporting ORION's objectives and addressing project challenges.

2. General System Description

The ORION project introduces a modular and scalable digital architecture to integrate advanced data analytics, Digital Twins (DTs), and artificial intelligence (AI) tools into the energy sector. By leveraging cutting-edge digital technologies, the system enhances operational efficiency, decision-making, and predictive capabilities in renewable energy management.

The ORION system's core consists of a flexible toolbox that facilitates secure data exchange, real-time monitoring, and seamless interoperability between various components and stakeholders. This architecture ensures adaptability across different energy environments while complying with international standards and regulations.

A key aspect of the system is its ability to provide data-driven insights for optimizing renewable energy assets, enabling more efficient resource utilization and improving overall system reliability. Designed with scalability and security, the ORION framework supports many users, including technical teams, regulatory bodies, and industry stakeholders, ensuring its applicability across different energy contexts.

This chapter provides an overview of the ORION system, detailing its structure, main features, and the stakeholders involved in its development and operation.

2.1. Overview of the ORION Modular Toolbox

The ORION Modular Toolbox is a scalable and interoperable digital framework designed to enhance the management and optimization of renewable energy assets. Integrating advanced data analytics, digital twins (DTs), and AI-based tools improves energy system monitoring, decision-making, and operational efficiency.

With the increasing complexity of renewable energy systems, digitalization and automation have become essential for ensuring their reliability and efficiency. However, these advances also introduce challenges, including efficient data management, system interoperability, and decision-making based on large-scale insights. ORION addresses these challenges through a modular and adaptable architecture that seamlessly integrates hydro, solar, wind, and wave energy assets. Furthermore, it ensures compatibility with leading European platforms.

Designed to support five distinct use cases, the ORION Toolbox balances standardization with adaptability. While all cases rely on core functionalities—such as system monitoring, AI-driven analytics, and Digital Twin integration—

the system allows customization to meet specific requirements, ensuring compliance across different energy assets and regulatory frameworks.

AI-based analytics and digital twin models play a pivotal role in ORION's ability to enhance real-time decision-making, facilitate proactive system adjustments, and improve forecasting accuracy. Additionally, robust data governance mechanisms ensure compliance with international regulations, including GDPR and specific policies in Cabo Verde, Brazil, and Canada.

Beyond its technological innovations, ORION is a key enabler of the energy transition. By optimizing the operation of renewable energy assets, it increases efficiency, reliability, and flexibility—ultimately reducing dependence on fossil fuels. Moreover, by providing a standardized digital ecosystem, ORION fosters stakeholder collaboration, drives innovation, supports policy development, and strengthens business integration within the renewable energy sector.

2.2. Main Features

The ORION architecture is designed to support a set of core functionalities that ensure efficient management, integration, and optimization of renewable energy assets. These functionalities enable data-driven decision-making, monitoring, and secure interoperability across energy systems. The key capabilities of the architecture include:

- Data Collection and Processing – Aggregating historical data from diverse energy assets and external sources.
- Interoperability and Standardization – Integration with European digital platforms and industry standards.
- Digital Twin Integration – Simulation and modelling of energy systems to improve forecasting, decision-making, and operational resilience.
- AI-Driven Analytics – Application of machine learning algorithms for anomaly detection, predictive maintenance, and optimization of energy flows.
- Monitoring and Control – Regularly tracking SCADA data and simulated DTs enables system analysis and proactive responses to operational conditions.
- Cybersecurity and Data Governance – Implement secure data-sharing protocols in compliance with GDPR and international regulations.
- Scalability and Modularity – Ability to adapt to different energy environments and expand with new functionalities as required.

2.3. Stakeholders and Users

The ORION Modular Toolbox is designed to serve a diverse range of users, each contributing to its development, implementation, and application in different

capacities. To ensure its effectiveness and broad applicability, the system engages key actors across multiple sectors, each contributing according to their expertise and capabilities.

- Research Institutions and Technology Developers – Responsible for the core development of ORION's functionalities, including AI models, Digital Twins, and data processing frameworks. These partners drive innovation, ensuring the system remains at the forefront of technological advancements.
- Energy Operators and Utilities – Leverage ORION's advanced analytics, monitoring, and decision-support capabilities to optimize energy generation, distribution and grid integration. Their feedback is crucial for refining ORION's functionalities to meet industry requirements.
- Regulatory Bodies and Policymakers – Establish and enforce regulatory compliance, shaping data governance regulations and policies that facilitate the energy sector's digital transformation. Their role is pivotal in ensuring ORION aligns with evolving European and global energy policies.
- Industry Partners and Technology Providers – Bridge the gap between research and real-world development. These partners contribute to integrating ORION into existing energy infrastructures, providing interoperability, cybersecurity, and operational resilience expertise, ensuring seamless adoption.
- Communities and End Users – The ultimate beneficiaries of ORION's innovations, experiencing improved renewable energy reliability, enhanced efficiency, and a more sustainable energy transition. Their engagement ensures the system remains user-centric and responsive to society's needs.

ORION's diverse partnerships ensure that the system is developed, tested and applied in real-world energy scenarios. Research institutions such as SINTEF, INOVA, INESC TEC, IMT, RWTH, ALBE, UFRJ, AUGM and UTA lead the management, development and validation of ORION's core technologies, including Digital Twins, AI-driven analytics, and data interoperability frameworks. Industry partners like EDP, SUAS and SIGMA ENERGIJA focus on deployment, integration, and operational feasibility. The project features five use cases spanning different energy sources – hydropower, solar, and wave energy – and different countries worldwide – Brazil, Canada, Cape Verde, Norway, Portugal and Slovenia – each requiring distinct adaptations of ORION's modular components.

2.4. ORION Use Cases and Architectural Adaptations

The ORION architecture is designed to support diverse energy environments by adapting to the specific needs of multiple use cases. While the core system

remains modular and interoperable, each use case requires customizations to optimize its digitalization strategy.

The ORION infrastructure is prepared to receive data and run simulation models and AI algorithms, allowing a flexible geometry approach for each use case. This results in different integration levels according to use case-specific requirements. Use cases in Norway/Cape Verde, Portugal, and Slovenia shall provide the ORION platform with data and rely on algorithms to run on the cloud-based platform. Due to their specificities, in some cases, such as in Canada and Brazil, advanced models, algorithms, and simulations are executed externally in university research centres, industrial cloud platforms, or national energy labs. ORION serves as a data exchange hub, ensuring structured input and output data flow between external computation environments and the platform's visualisation and decision-support tools.

For the latter cases, input data (such as sensor readings, SCADA outputs, and operational logs) is collected and transmitted to external AI processing environments. Algorithms and simulations are run externally to the platform. The processed results are then stored back into ORION for further visualisation and decision-making. This architecture ensures data remains accessible and structured while computational processes remain external to ORION.

The following use cases highlight the flexibility of ORION's architecture and its ability to integrate with external infrastructures, AI models, and decision-support systems.

Table 1 - Use Case-Specific Adaptability of the ORION Platform

Use Case	Main Focus	Key Adaptations in ORION
Norway & Cape Verde (UC1)	Decarbonisation of port cities by increasing onshore RES share.	ORION will support RES planning and optimise operation, leading to decarbonisation.
Portugal (UC2)	AI-enhanced monitoring and maintenance of PV plants.	ORION integrates AI models for fault detection and analysis in PV systems, supporting analytics.
Slovenia (UC3)	Structural health monitoring for offshore wave energy.	ORION integrates sensor-based condition monitoring with DT visualization.
Brazil (UC4)	Geographically Distributed Co-Simulation (GDS) for real-time energy system analysis.	Co-simulation algorithms are run in different locations, locally. Results are conveyed to the ORION platform for DT integration.
Canada (UC5)	AI-driven fault detection and predictive maintenance for power generation.	Models/algorithms are run externally; ORION acts as a data exchange hub for structured input/output.

Use case 1 comprises two ports connected to electric networks, with different levels of renewable energy integration and onshore power supply to vessels. In both cases, vessel characteristics and power measurements are input into the ORION platform. In Aalesund, Norway, renewable resources and charging stations have already been installed, and optimisation algorithms may run on existing data. However, a significant urban expansion in the surrounding area and an increase in the onshore power supply require an increase in electricity demand, which, in turn, makes the decarbonisation objective even more challenging. In Mindelo, Cape Verde, there are some renewable sources but no onshore power supply, so optimisation must consider scenarios based on existing data and estimates. Both power demand, namely due to onshore power supply, and renewable energy available due to additional rooftop PV panels increase throughout the project. Information provided asynchronously to the ORION platform includes measured data, estimates, and planning specifications. The optimisation algorithms for both cases in present and future scenarios run on the ORION platform.

In use case 2, the platform receives measured and forecast data synchronously or near-synchronously. Physical models and AI model training run locally and are then uploaded to the ORION platform. The AI fault analysis algorithms run on the ORION platform.

In use case 3, sensor data is received and pre-processed locally due to the high sampling frequency of some measured quantities. Pre-processed data is then uploaded to the ORION platform in bursts, which are compatible with the size and time scale of the data to be sent. Further data processing and vibration data analysis algorithms run on the ORION platform.

Use case 4 follows a Geographically Distributed Co-Simulation (GDS) approach, where stakeholders such as ONS and LAFAE execute their simulations locally in their respective infrastructures. Unlike other ORION-integrated models, use case 4 simulations are not performed within the ORION platform but instead rely on the platform for structured input data exchange and results upload for visualisation and decision support. Similarly, data exchange between ORION and the external computational environments occurs asynchronously in this use case.

In use case 5, data processing, algorithms, and simulations run locally, conveying relevant input data and results to the ORION platform asynchronously. The ORION platform serves as a centralized repository for structured data exchange, allowing stakeholders to download input datasets and upload computed results for further analysis and visualization. This ensures flexibility while maintaining consistency across multiple simulation environments.

3. General Architecture

3.1. High-level System Requirements

Figure 1 - Layered Architecture

The proposed architecture is designed to integrate five layers, from use cases to users, passing through the main goal of this project, the Orion Cloud-Based Platform.

The layered architecture defines the high-level responsibilities, establishing each layer's functions in the ecosystem. Each layer provides a dataset that is loaded and transformed, with the goal of mashup and normalization for the subsequent layer. This process is repeated until the analysis results are obtained, supporting user decision-making and enabling a user-friendly visualization of the information.

The conceptual definition of each layer of the high-level ORION architecture is presented below.

- ❖ Use Cases - Defines how different partners interact with the architecture.
- ❖ Ingestion and Processing Layer - Collects, transforms, and prepares data for analysis and storage.
- ❖ Processing & Analytics Layer - Utilizes AI models, Digital Twins, optimisation and forecasting algorithms, and simulation models for data analysis, fault prediction, and system optimisation.
- ❖ Data Storage and Management - Centrally stores and structurally organises data for processing and analytics.

- ❖ Interface & Visualization Layer - Provides an intuitive and user-friendly interface through dashboards, charts, visualisation tools, monitoring tools, and simulation platforms, enabling easy navigation and quick decision-making.
- ❖ Users - Refers to the end users interacting with the platform to access analyses, insights, and results for informed decision-making.

3.2. High-level Architecture Design

Given the complexity of integrating multiple data sources, processing information efficiently, and delivering meaningful insights, a structured architecture is essential for the ORION platform. Figure 1 presents ORION's high-level architecture, depicting the key agents within the ecosystem, their interactions, and the main layers that support data ingestion, processing, storage, and visualisation. This architecture enables seamless information flow, facilitating efficient analysis and decision-making. The following sections will explore each layer in detail, along with their components, connections, and data flow across the platform.

Figure 2 - High-level Architecture

3.2.1 Use cases and Data Sources

Within the context of the use cases, there are two main actors: the data owners, who are responsible for providing the data, and the research institutions and specialists, who utilise them as inputs for advanced analysis tools. The outputs of these analyses serve as decision-support tools and enhance the management of energy assets.

The results derived from data processing and analysis are applied in several areas, including decarbonisation support, energy infrastructure optimisation, fault diagnosis and classification in photovoltaic power plants, operational efficiency improvement, emissions reduction, optimisation of hybrid energy system operations, and the integration of renewable energy sources into the energy matrix.

Diverse data sources are leveraged to enable these analyses, including information extracted from SCADA, CSV/Excel files, meteorological data, and energy monitoring systems. Additionally, performance data from electrical and digital systems collected by research centres and testing laboratories provide essential insights for a comprehensive assessment of energy systems.

3.2.2 Data Ingestion and Processing

This layer is responsible for the initial processing of data, ensuring that raw information from various sources is organized, cleaned, and efficiently made available for the upper layers of the ORION system. This layer prepares data for advanced analytics, such as fault detection, energy optimisation, and predictive maintenance, by ensuring reliability and consistency.

The ingestion process gathers data from multiple sources, including SCADA systems, IoT devices, historical databases, external APIs, and digital platforms. It supports real-time streaming and batch processing, allowing flexible handling of diverse data types.

After ingestion, data undergoes cleaning and transformation to enhance quality and reliability. This includes normalisation, standardisation, and conversion into compatible formats. Filtering mechanisms eliminate null values, duplicates, and inconsistencies, while error correction and gap-filling techniques, such as interpolation or statistical methods, address missing data.

When applicable, an integration phase can merge information from different sources to enrich the dataset, incorporating climate data, operational records, and market trends. This contextualised approach enables deeper insights and more accurate analytics.

A temporary storage and buffering mechanism ensures fault tolerance and prevents data loss, maintaining availability even during system failures or network disruptions.

Finally, the processed data is routed to higher-level applications, including AI models, digital twins, and decision-support systems. It is transferred to data lakes, warehouses, or specialised databases, ensuring structured and accessible information for critical decision-making in ORION.

3.2.3 Processing & Analytics Layer

The Processing & Analytics layer of the ORION Cloud Base Platform is responsible for advanced data processing, integrating artificial intelligence algorithms, analytical models, and co-simulation techniques to enhance operational efficiency, fault detection, and process optimisation. This layer analyses and processes data stored in the Data Lake, enabling the application of methodologies developed by research institutions and industry experts.

Data reaches this layer after being collected from various external sources. Initially, it passes through the Data Ingestion process, where it is organised, standardised, and stored in the Data Lake. AI algorithms and analytical models process the information from this central repository, enabling advanced simulations and predictive analysis.

Data enters the system via APIs and ingestion mechanisms, ensuring seamless connectivity between use cases and ORION's infrastructure. The Processing & Analytics layer receives this data, runs algorithms, applies computational models, and performs co-simulations, making the results available in the database. The outputs of this layer include analytical results, reports, fault alerts, and operational forecasts, which are accessible via APIs and integrated into platforms such as the Graphical Digital Twin and monitoring and reporting systems.

The Processing & Analytics module ensures interoperability by adopting international standards and a modular architecture, enabling the continuous integration of new algorithms and analytical tools. As a result, this layer performs advanced analyses and continuously evolves, incorporating emerging techniques and methodologies as they are developed.

3.2.4 Data Storage and Management

The Data Storage and Management layer is responsible for storing and managing data, ensuring it remains accessible, structured, and secure for further analysis.

This layer follows international standards for data normalisation and structured storage to ensure interoperability and consistency. These standards facilitate integration with various applications, analytics tools, and external systems. The architecture supports different storage formats, including structured, semi-structured, and unstructured data, allowing flexibility in handling diverse datasets.

A data lake architecture is implemented, enabling the storage of large volumes of heterogeneous data while maintaining efficient retrieval capabilities. This approach ensures that real-time and historical data are

readily available for analytics, AI models, digital twins, and decision-support systems.

In addition to storage, this layer must incorporate data governance and security measures, enforcing access controls, encryption, and compliance with regulatory requirements. Fault tolerance mechanisms and backup strategies are also in place to prevent data loss and ensure high availability.

By structuring and organising data effectively, this layer enhances the reliability and usability of insights generated within the ORION platform.

3.2.5 Interface & Visualization Layer

The Graphical Digital Twin and Visualization layer provides an advanced interface for analysing, visualising, and simulating operational scenarios based on collected and processed data. This layer enhances decision-making by offering dynamic and interactive environments that facilitate monitoring and in-depth data analysis.

A visualisation engine is developed to achieve this, supporting dynamic and interactive interfaces, including augmented and virtual reality applications. Platforms such as AUGMENTCITY can enable immersive visualisations of operational scenarios, allowing a comprehensive understanding of system behaviour and optimisation opportunities.

Advanced visualisation techniques, including heatmaps, time series analysis, and data modelling, are implemented to present complex datasets intuitively. These tools help identify patterns, anomalies, and trends, improving the accuracy of diagnostics and predictive insights.

Additionally, the Orion Platform ensures seamless integration with external stakeholders through Electronic Document Interchange (EDI), utilising APIs, FTP, and other relevant protocols. This guarantees interoperability and efficient data exchange between systems.

At its core, this layer processes data using specialised tools to create a responsive and intuitive interface, ensuring efficient visualisation, monitoring, and decision-making. Combining interactive elements with robust analytics empowers stakeholders with actionable insights, contributing to a more informed and optimized operational strategy.

3.3. Multi-Use Case Adaptability

The ORION architecture is built to support five distinct use cases across different energy systems, ensuring a balance between standardization and flexibility. To achieve this, the architecture follows these principles:

- **Modular Design:** Components can be selectively activated or reconfigured depending on the specific requirements of each use case.
- **Interoperability Layer:** Ensures seamless integration across different platforms while accommodating case-specific APIs and data formats.
- **Governance and Access Control:** Implements role-based access and data segmentation strategies to manage shared and case-specific datasets securely.
- **Common Data Models & Standardization:** Encourages uniformity in data collection and processing across all cases while allowing custom extensions for unique operational needs.
- **Scalability & Replicability:** Designed to be easily extended to additional cases beyond the initial five, facilitating long-term adoption in new scenarios.

Each use case benefits from a common core architecture, but adaptations are necessary based on factors such as:

Table 2 - Adaptation Drivers and Common Architectural Elements in ORION

Factor	Common Elements	Use-Case Specific Adaptations
Energy Source	AI analytics Digital Twins, Cybersecurity	Hydro, solar, and wave energy have unique operational constraints
Data Governance	GDPR Compliance Secure APIs	Regional regulations vary for Cape Verde, Brazil, and Canada
System Integration	Standardised API structure	Custom data exchange protocols for different platforms
End-User Interaction	Monitoring dashboards Decision-support tools	Specific features tailored to the needs of each use case

In Table 2, each column addresses a different aspect of the ORION architecture. The 'Factor' column highlights the general elements influencing how the architecture should be adapted. The 'Common Elements' column outlines the shared components or core features used across all use cases within the ORION project, regardless of their regional or operational differences. The 'Use-Case Specific Adaptations' column focuses on the adjustments required for each specific use case, such as those in Brazil, Canada, and Cape Verde, considering the unique characteristics of each region or application.

➤ Energy Source

- Common Elements: All use cases share foundational elements such as AI analytics, Digital Twins, and cybersecurity measures.
- Use-Case Specific Adaptations: Different energy sources, such as hydropower, solar, and wind, have unique operational constraints that must be accounted for in the architecture. These include varying monitoring and optimisation requirements essential for system efficiency.

➤ Data Governance

- Common Elements: Data governance ensures compliance with GDPR, meaning all data must be processed according to data protection standards using secure APIs.
- Use-Case Specific Adaptations: Regional data protection and privacy regulations vary by country or region (e.g., Cape Verde, Brazil, and Canada). Each location has specific rules and policies to consider when implementing the system.

➤ System Integration

- Common Elements: The ORION project follows a standardised API structure for system integration, allowing seamless communication between all systems within the platform.
- Use-Case Specific Adaptations: Depending on the particular use case, the data exchange protocols must be adapted to suit the specific platforms or systems associated with each region or energy source.

➤ End-User Interaction

- Common Elements: All use cases incorporate monitoring dashboards and decision-support tools that enable user interaction with the system, allowing for data visualisation and informed decision-making.
- Use-Case Specific Adaptations: Each use case may include features tailored to the needs of different users, such as plant operators or regulators. As a result, the way data is visualised and how users engage with the platform may vary depending on these specific needs.

Combining a structured yet flexible design, the ORION architecture promotes synergy across use cases, reduces development complexity, and facilitates scalability and replication beyond the project's initial scope. While ORION adheres to a core architecture, it is also designed to accommodate various computational strategies. For example, the Canada use case relies on the

external execution of AI models, and the Brazil use case performs co-simulations locally using external infrastructures. Similar approaches may also be applied in other use cases, where external execution or local simulations are used depending on the specific requirements. In these cases, ORION acts as a central hub for structured data exchange rather than as an execution environment.

Key architectural considerations include:

- Role-Based Access Control (RBAC): Ensures secure data exchange while allowing partners to maintain control over externally executed models.
- External API Support: Adapts ORION's API framework to connect with cloud-based platforms and real-time co-simulation tools.
- Data Harmonization & Standardization: Implements structured data ingestion, processing, and retrieval mechanisms for interoperability across cases with different execution strategies.

These governance principles ensure that ORION remains scalable, interoperable, and adaptable to various computational environments.

4. Internal and External Communications

The API framework in ORION is designed to support multiple use cases simultaneously while maintaining a unified interface for data exchange. To accommodate case-specific variations, the system implements dynamic API configurations, allowing modules to be selectively enabled or customised based on the specific requirements of each use case. These APIs are critical in interoperability, facilitating data integration, secure communication, and real-time monitoring within the ORION ecosystem.

Research institutions (such as INESC TEC, IMT, UFRJ, and the University of Alberta) contribute to developing analytical models and AI-based tools for asset monitoring and data processing. RWTH Aachen, as the core developer of the ORION platform architecture, ensures its modular design and interoperability. In parallel, technology developers (including AUGMENTCITY) focus on implementing backend infrastructures, analytical APIs, and user interfaces. Together, these efforts enable the integration with Digital Twin platforms to support predictive analytics and informed decision-making across diverse energy use cases.

The primary stakeholders responsible for ORION's API infrastructure include:

- Research Institutions and Technology Developers – Focused on AI model development and analytical API integration.
- Industry Partners and Technology Providers – Responsible for API interoperability, security, and integration with external platforms.
- Energy Operators – Utilize APIs for grid monitoring, energy optimisation, and predictive analytics.
- Regulatory Bodies – Ensure API compliance with cybersecurity and data governance regulations.

By leveraging a robust and scalable API architecture, ORION ensures efficient data exchange, integration across energy systems, and enhanced decision-making capabilities for all stakeholders involved in the energy transition.

4.1. Internal APIs

The internal API structure in ORION is designed to facilitate communication between system modules, ensuring efficient data flow and computational interoperability. These APIs enable structured data ingestion, processing, and retrieval within the platform, supporting diverse analytical and operational needs. Given ORION's modular nature, the internal API ecosystem maintains a unified interface while allowing for dynamic configurations based on specific use cases.

Each ORION use case relies on internal APIs for distinct functionalities, enabling real-time data exchange between Artificial Intelligence (AI) models, Digital Twins, monitoring systems, and data repositories. Key functionalities include:

- Canada & Brazil: Standardizes structured data inputs for external AI models before visualisation and analysis in ORION.
- Portugal: Aggregates SCADA and meteorological datasets to support real-time photovoltaic (PV) diagnostics and fault detection.
- Norway & Cape Verde: Facilitates vessel and buildings energy consumption monitoring and renewable energy integration data processing.
- Slovenia: Transfers sensor-generated predictive maintenance data for offshore energy assets.

In the Brazilian use case, internal APIs ensure a structured input and output data exchange between ORION and external simulation environments:

- Data Preparation: APIs enable local simulation platforms to download datasets structured within ORION.
- Result Upload & Retrieval: APIs manage the upload of processed simulation outputs, allowing further analysis within ORION's framework.

ORION's internal APIs are restricted to the system environment and inaccessible to external platforms. They play a crucial role in data integration, connecting Artificial Intelligence models, Digital Twin simulations, and operational monitoring systems. ORION's internal interactions facilitate structured communication between system components, supporting advanced energy analytics and operational optimisation.

To ensure data integrity and cybersecurity, ORION's internal API framework enforces Role-Based Access Control (RBAC), establishing specific access rules according to the operational context of each use case. For use cases where AI models are executed within the ORION platform, RBAC guarantees that energy analytics are processed in a secure, closed environment with controlled access. For use cases that require external data exchange, such as those implemented in Canada and Brazil, RBAC policies regulate API interactions, ensuring that data transmission between ORION and external AI platforms is performed securely and complies with applicable regulations.

In conclusion, the internal API ecosystem in ORION ensures modular, scalable, and efficient data exchange between core computational components. By integrating AI, Digital Twins, and monitoring systems through high-performance APIs, ORION enhances predictive analytics, operational efficiency, and energy system optimization across diverse geographical use cases.

4.2. External APIs

The ORION platform is designed to connect with external systems, ensuring interoperability, security, and compliance with international standards. External APIs enable data exchange between ORION and third-party platforms, regulatory entities, and industrial partners, facilitating real-time data sharing, visualization, and analytical integration.

ORION's API architecture supports a flexible, multi-protocol communication layer, utilizing:

- RESTful APIs for standard web-based interactions and scalable data retrieval.
- GraphQL APIs for optimized, query-based data access, improving efficiency in analytical applications.
- Electronic Data Interchange (EDI) protocols, ensuring secure, structured data exchange between ORION's ecosystem and third-party stakeholders.

ORION applies strict security measures to ensure the protection of its data and services. These measures include using OAuth 2.0 and API keys for user authentication, implementing TLS encryption to safeguard data in transit, and adopting role-based access control (RBAC) to limit API usage according to user privileges.

The External APIs connect ORION with major European and international energy and data-sharing platforms, ensuring broad accessibility and data interoperability. The primary external integrations include:

- 1. GAIA-X Cloud Infrastructure:** Provides secure, federated cloud computing for energy data applications. Guarantees compliance with European data governance frameworks while enabling high-performance cloud processing of ORION's analytical outputs.
- 2. FIWARE Open Source IoT Framework:** Supports data exchange with IoT devices and smart energy systems. ORION's FIWARE-integrated APIs allows the synchronisation of energy monitoring and predictive maintenance tools.
- 3. AUGMENTCITY (AUGM) Visualization & Simulation APIs:** Integrates ORION with digital twin environments for scenario modelling. Provide interactive dashboards and predictive analytics for energy system optimisation.

ORION's APIs are tailored for specific geographical and operational contexts, supporting different energy applications:

- Canada & Brazil: Secure transfer of structured input/output data between ORION and external AI-powered platforms for energy optimisation.

- Portugal: SCADA and PV asset management platforms integrated with ORION for energy monitoring.
- Norway & Cape Verde: Smart port energy management APIs enabling predictive maintenance and grid stability assessments.
- Slovenia: APIs designed for structural monitoring of offshore energy assets, ensuring safety and operational efficiency.

The external API ecosystem in ORION ensures data interoperability with external platforms and systems, enabling scalable, secure, and efficient energy data exchange across multiple stakeholders and geographies while complying with international standards.

4.3. Data Flow Diagram

Show how data flows between internal and external components.

High Level Data Flow - Orion Architecture

A flow of data through entities and systems on Orion ecosystem

Figure 3 - High-Level Data Flow

The ORION platform follows a structured data flow to ensure the efficient exchange of information between internal and external components. The High-Level Data Flow Diagram (Figure 3) illustrates the journey of data from its initial collection to its final application, ensuring integration across different systems. The process follows a linear and structured pipeline, where data from multiple sources is processed, stored, and made accessible through APIs for Digital Twin simulations and user applications.

The data flow begins with Use Case Data, which originates from multiple sources such as SCADA systems, IoT devices, meteorological databases, and other energy monitoring systems. This raw data is transmitted through multiple standards using API/EDI mechanisms, ensuring compatibility and secure communication between stakeholders. Once collected, these datasets are forwarded to the Processing & Analytics Layer, which is analysed using AI models, simulations, and co-simulation techniques. The processed outputs are stored in the ORION Data Lake and become accessible via APIs for end-users.

This processed information is fed into the Digital Twin environment through APIs, enabling real-time visualization, operational simulations, and predictive

analytics. The Digital Twin provides stakeholders an interactive interface to monitor energy systems, analyse performance, and optimize decision-making. The final step in the data flow involves the User Application, where end-users can access processed insights, visualizations, and system recommendations. Users interact with the system through advanced interfaces, including Digital Twins and dashboards, supporting real-time analysis, reporting, and decision-making. These applications ensure that ORION's data-driven insights translate into actionable strategies.

By structuring the data flow this way, ORION ensures that raw data is efficiently transformed into meaningful insights, supporting energy optimization, fault detection, and renewable integration. This end-to-end architecture enables seamless interaction between data sources, cloud-based analytics, Digital Twin simulations, and user applications, ensuring that stakeholders receive accurate and actionable information in real-time.

5. Technical Specifications of Components

The technical specifications of each module will be defined progressively throughout the project, in line with the development and implementation of each module. These specifications will be incorporated into this document as it evolves, expected to be finalized by the deadline established for the completion of the final version of this document, scheduled for Project Month 20.

A structured API framework will be followed, organized into three key components: (i) Component Descriptions, detailing the purpose and functionality of each element; (ii) Configuration and Integration, describing how the components are configured and interconnected within the overall architecture; and (iii) Constraints and Assumptions, outlining the limitations, dependencies, and key assumptions considered in the design and implementation of the system.

6. Security and Compliance

The ORION platform adopts a security-by-design approach to ensure that all data communications—whether internal or external—are managed securely and following international best practices. The proposed architecture incorporates a comprehensive framework that includes security mechanisms, governance policies, and regulatory alignment to protect system integrity and user data throughout the platform's lifecycle.

6.1. Security Policies

The architecture implements robust security policies to manage authentication, authorization, and data protection across all system layers. Internal APIs support interactions among ORION's modular components—such as AI models, Digital Twins, and analytics engines—within a protected environment. These interactions follow Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) policies, ensuring access is restricted based on predefined user roles.

For use cases requiring external processing—such as Brazil and Canada—data exchange is handled through structured API interactions governed by the same RBAC principles, ensuring traceability and control across international boundaries.

External communications follow a multi-protocol approach, integrating RESTful and GraphQL APIs to ensure interoperability and fine-grained access control. These APIs are protected using OAuth 2.0 authentication, API key management, and TLS encryption, safeguarding data in transit and access endpoints.

A dedicated data governance framework supports these policies, as defined in Deliverable D2.1 – Data Management Plan. This includes appointing a Data Protection Officer (DPO) (SINTEF), naming data contact points within each partner, and assigning data processing responsibilities to use case leaders. Additional protective measures, such as pseudonymisation, encryption, and NDA enforcement, are implemented to reduce the risk of data breaches or misuse, especially for sensitive or commercially relevant data.

6.2. Compliance with Standards

ORION's architecture aligns with key international regulations and technical standards to ensure lawful and ethical data handling. Foremost among these is the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which guides all policies related to personal data processing, access, and user rights.

In addition to GDPR, specific technical standards such as IEC 61724 are applied in use cases involving photovoltaic asset monitoring and performance analysis. Moreover, ORION follows the principles of ISO/IEC 27001 for information security management, particularly regarding risk assessment, incident response, and the continuous improvement of security processes.

To support compliance, ORION implements a systematic risk management process introduced in the Project Handbook (D1.1) and detailed in D2.1 (Section 4.6). This includes identifying, evaluating, mitigating, and monitoring security risks across the project's duration and scope, ensuring resilience and accountability at every level of implementation.

7. Evolution Plan

This section outlines the evolution strategy for the ORION architecture, ensuring its continuous improvement and alignment with project objectives. As this is the first version of the architecture report, the current specification provides the foundational framework that will be progressively refined. Future iterations will incorporate feedback from technical partners and stakeholders and practical insights gathered during the implementation of the five use cases.

The evolution plan focuses on technical consolidation, functional enrichment, and operational validation, ensuring the architecture remains adaptable, scalable, and compliant with emerging standards and project needs. The final version of this deliverable, foreseen for Project Month 20, will include the complete architecture, detailed technical specifications, and validated integration procedures.

7.1. Foreseen Improvements

The next version of this document (Version 2) will address specific areas of enhancement and technical detailing. The following improvements and developments are foreseen:

- **Definition of Technological Components:** The future version will specify the technological components and platforms selected for implementing the ORION architecture, including cloud infrastructure, communication protocols, and data processing environments.
- **Detailed Implementation Strategy:** Additional information regarding each module's software and hardware solutions will be incorporated, ensuring a clear understanding of the operational environment and technical dependencies.
- **Enhanced Stakeholder Role Mapping:** The interactions and responsibilities of each stakeholder group will be further detailed, clarifying their specific roles in the development, deployment, and use of the ORION Modular Toolbox.
- **Use Case-Specific Customizations:** Functional and architectural adaptations required for each use case will be clearly defined, ensuring that the modular components address each scenario's specific needs and operational constraints.
- **Integration Procedures:** A more comprehensive description of the procedures for the configuration, integration, and validation of each module will be provided, including testing protocols and performance benchmarks.
- **Security and Compliance Updates:** The security framework will be expanded with implementation details, ensuring compliance with GDPR, ISO/IEC 27001, and other relevant regulations across all project geographies.

- Continuous Feedback Incorporation: Improvements identified during the validation activities and feedback from stakeholders and end users will be integrated to ensure the architecture's robustness and usability.
- Alignment with Emerging Standards: The architecture will be updated to incorporate new standards or best practices in data governance, interoperability, and digitalization of the energy sector as they become available during the project execution.

The objective is to ensure that the ORION Modular Toolbox architecture evolves consistently with technological advancements, stakeholder needs, and the practical results obtained from implementing the use cases.

8. Conclusion

This deliverable establishes a structured and adaptable framework for the ORION Modular Toolbox, ensuring that all use cases benefit from a common set of digitalization tools while allowing necessary architectural customizations. The ORION Modular Toolbox is designed for interoperability across different energy systems and scalability, replicability, and adaptability beyond the scope of the current use cases.

A key aspect of ORION's flexibility is its ability to support both integrated AI processing and externally executed models, as demonstrated in the use cases of Canada and Brazil. Through flexible API integrations, role-based data governance, and AI-driven decision support, ORION can enhance renewable energy operations, optimise predictive maintenance, and support real-time energy market decisions across multiple global scenarios.

This document constitutes the initial version and will undergo continuous refinement and incremental updates throughout the project's development cycle, with its final version (Version 2) planned for delivery in Project Month 20.

